

CHEMOTHERAPY OF BACTERIAL INFECTIONS. PART I. SUBSTANCES RELATED TO SULPHANILAMIDE. SYNTHESIS OF *p*-AMINOBENZYL SULPHONAMIDE AND ITS DERIVATIVES

BY P. L. NARASIMHA RAO.

p-Aminobenzylsulphonamide and its derivatives have been prepared for pharmacological study with a view to throwing further light on the relation between chemical constitution and antistreptococcal action as well as the mechanism of chemotherapeutic action of sulphanilamide drugs.

The specific antistreptococcal action of the red-dye, prontosil (hydrochloride of 4-sulphamido-2':4'-diaminoazobenzene (I, R=H), (Domagk, *Deut. Med. Wschr.*, 1935, **61**, 250; *Z. angew. Chem.*, 1935, **48**, 657; *Klin. Wschr.*, 1936, **15**, 1585), and the striking therapeutic effect of the previously known simpler compound, sulphanilamide, (II, R=R'=H) and many of its derivatives of the type R-NH SO₂R' in various bac-

terial infections have stimulated widespread interest and renewed activity in chemotherapy of infectious disease. Thus there have come into medical practice a host of sulphanilamide derivative like prontosil sol (III), rubiazol (I, R=CO₂Na), septazine (II, R=C₆H₅CH₂; R'=H), soluseptazine (IV) for use in cases of erysipelus, strept. angina, puerperal sepsis, strept. meningitis, etc. Apart from these,

(IV)

sulphanilamide drugs have also been used with success in the treatment of coli infections of genito-urinary tract (due to *B. coli* and *Proteus ammoniae*) and in that of pneumococcus and meningococcus infections. Some sulphanilamide derivatives containing substituted residues in the sulphonamide group are shown to be active in the staphylococcal, anaerobic and above all in gonococcal infections. Of these compounds uleron (Baeyer), 4-(4'-amino-benzene)-sulphonamidobenzenesulphonyl

dimethylamine (II, R=H; R' = - C_6H_{10} SO₂NMe₂) and albucid (Schering) (II, R=H; R'=COMe) find favour in the treatment of gonorrhoea.

(V)

(VI)

Perhaps the greatest achievement in this line lies in the discovery of sulphapyridine (V) (M. and B. 693; Dagenan) for the treatment of pneumococcal pneumonia and to lesser extent also meningitis staphylococcal septicemia, chronic meningococcal septicemia, subacute bacterial endocarditis and also pemphigus.

It is clear from the foregoing that researches in this branch of chemotherapy are progressing on two main lines namely towards the preparation of (i) drugs more effective and less toxic than sulphanilamide, and (ii) drugs effective in bacterial and virus infections in which sulphanilamide and its derivatives fail.

This investigation has been undertaken with the object of following the course of the above two lines. Firstly it is intended to prepare new type of compounds but closely related to sulphanilamide and test their therapeutic action against bacterial infections especially against those not responding favourably with known drugs. It is also proposed to prepare some new derivatives of sulphanilamide likely to possess antibacterial activity.

Till now most of the drugs employed for the treatment of bacterial infections contain sulphur and all the recent drugs of sulphanilamide group possess sulphur residues directly attached to the benzene nucleus. However, Buttle and his collaborators (*Biochem. J.*, 1938, **32**, 1101; cf. Marshall, *Physiol. Rev.*, 1939, **19**, 240) state that 4:4'-dinitrodiphenylmethane, 4:4'-dinitrodiphenyl oxide, and 2:2'-dinitro-4: 4'-diaminodiphenylmethane possess some activity and Bittenbunder and Degaring (*J. Amer. Pharm. Assoc.*, 1939, **28**, 515) recently report bacteriostatic effect of *para*-substituted phenyl. acetic acid derivatives on staphylococcus aureus and *E. coli* in *vitro*. In the light of these observations it was thought of interest, in the first place, to ascertain what bactericidal activity the compounds of the type (VI) having an aliphatic side-chain between the benzene nucleus and the sulphonamido group possess and so *p*-aminobenzyl sulphonamide and some of its derivatives have now been prepared.

Marshall (*loc. cit.*) states "little or no activity is found in mononuclear compounds in which.....the sulphonamide group (is replaced) by groups *not yielding a sulphonic acid on oxidation.*" This statement may be of special significance since it is becoming known that oxidation products of sulphanilamide (Shaffer, *Science*, 1939, **89**, 547) are the real therapeutic agents *in vivo*. Hence it is evidently desirable to ascertain how the greater facility of oxidation of the sulphonamide group in *p*-aminobenzylsulphanilamide as compared to that in sulphanilamide, augments the activity of the latter. It is with this object in view a study of the oxidation potential of *p*-aminobenzylsulphonamide under conditions similar to those employed for sulphanilamide, is being actively pursued. The results of physico-chemical and the pharmacological experiments will be published in due course.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Sodium p-nitrobenzylsulphonate was conveniently prepared by the following modification of the method outlined in D. R. P., 55,138 (*Frdl.* II, 386; cf. Purgotti, Monti and Designs, *Gazzetta*, 1900, **30**, 247; Ingold *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 813).

A mixture of *p*-nitrobenzyl bromide (21.6 g.; chloride, 17.2 g.), anhydrous sodium sulphite (12.6 g.), water (100 c.c.) and alcohol (300 c.c.) was boiled under reflux till a fairly clear solution was obtained (6 hours). Alcohol was then removed by distillation and the solution after filtering

from a little tar, was concentrated to about 50 c.c. The sodium salt of the sulphonic acid that crystallised out was separated and recrystallised from alcohol, yield 20 g.

p-Nitrobenzylsulphonyl Chloride and Amide.—The acid chloride (Ingold, *loc. cit*) was purified by crystallisation from benzene-ligroin mixture. The amide (Mohr, *Annalen*, 1883 221, 218) was conveniently crystallised from dilute pyridine.

p-Aminobenzylsulphonamide was obtained by the reduction of the above nitrosulphonamide with ammonium sulphide or tin and hydrochloric acid. In the first method a mixture of the nitro compound (10 g.), alcohol (100 c.c.), water (50 c.c.) and liquor ammonia (30 c.c.) was saturated with hydrogen sulphide and then gently boiled for 1 hour under reflux. This procedure was repeated thrice adding more liquid ammonia, till the whole nitro compound went into solution. The product was then boiled with a little more water for a few minutes and concentrated after neutralisation with hydrochloric acid and filtration of the precipitated sulphur. On making the solution ammoniacal, the amino compound, m.p. 168°, separated in pale yellow powder which was recrystallised from hot water (charcoal) to which a few drops of ammonia were added to remove the persistent yellow colour, yield 5.4 g. (Found: N, 15.1; S, 17.2. $C_7H_{10}O_2N_2S$ requires N, 15.05; S, 17.20 per cent).

Reduction of the nitro compound with tin and hydrochloric acid in the usual way proceeded more smoothly and the yield of the amino compound was invariably better. It is easily soluble in hot water and pyridine, fairly in alcohol and difficultly in other usual organic solvents. Its solutions in dilute acids are pale yellow and its diazotised solution coupled easily with β -naphthol.

The amine rapidly turns yellow on exposure to air and its solutions often acquire a characteristic pinkish yellow colour on standing exposed to air and light. This is perhaps significant in the light of the statements of Shaffer about the oxidation products of sulphanilamide.

The acetyl derivative crystallised from hot water in colourless stout prism-like crystals, m.p. 212°. (Found: N, 12.2. $C_9H_{12}O_3N_2S$ requires N, 12.32 per cent). The valeryl derivative was obtained as colourless leaflets, m.p. 188-89°. (Found: N, 10.5. $C_{12}H_{14}O_3N_2S$ requires N, 10.33 per cent) and the caproyl derivative as silvery-white plates, m.p. 192-94°. (Found: N, 9.9. $C_{13}H_{20}O_3N_2S$ requires N, 9.86 per cent). They were both prepared

by the action of the respective acid chloride on the amine in pyridine solution and crystallising the products from dilute alcohol.

The *benzoyl derivative*, prepared in a similar manner, was sparingly soluble in many of the usual solvents and crystallised from alcohol in microscopic crystals, m.p. 230-31°. (Found : N, 9'5. $C_{14}H_{14}O_3N_2S$ requires N, 9'66 per cent).

The following derivatives substituted at the amino group of the above compound were prepared by condensing together equimolecular quantities of *p*-nitrobenzylsulphonamide and the appropriate amine in benzene solution in presence of pyridine, and the resulting nitro compounds were then reduced.

p-Nitrobenzylsulphanilide crystallised from pyridine, m.p. 130-31°. (Found : N, 9'8. $C_{13}H_{12}O_4N_2S$ requires N, 9'59 per cent).

p-Aminobenzylsulphanilide.—To a mixture of the above nitro compound (5 g.), granulated tin (10 g.), hydrochloric acid (20%, 30 c.c.) was added gradually with shaking and the product heated on a water-bath till the nitro compound went into solution. It was then diluted, filtered and freed from tin by precipitating it as tin sulphide. The concentrated filtrate deposited colourless feathery needles, the hydrochloride of *p*-aminobenzylsulphanilide melting at 168-70° (decomp.). (Found : N, 9'4. $C_{13}H_{14}O_2N_2S$, HCl requires N, 9'05 per cent). The hydrochloride was dissolved in water and made just ammoniacal whereupon the free base separated out. It was recrystallised from water in colourless plates, m.p. 172-73°. (Found : N, 10'7. $C_{13}H_{14}O_2N_2S$ requires N, 10'73 per cent).

p-Nitrobenzylsulphonyl-2-aminopyridine.—*p* Nitrobenzylsulphonyl chloride (4'8 g.) in benzene (20 c.c.) was gradually added under shaking to a solution of 2-aminopyridine (4'5 g.) in benzene (20 c.c.). The separated solid was filtered, washed with a little water and benzene and crystallised from pyridine. The nitro compound separated in colourless stout prisms, m.p. 214-15°, sparingly soluble in many of the ordinary solvents. (Found : N, 14'3. $C_{12}H_{11}O_4N_3S$ requires N, 14'33 per cent)

p-Aminobenzylsulphonyl-2-aminopyridine.—The reduction of the above nitro compound did not proceed satisfactorily with ammonium sulphide due to its low solubility. It, was, however, reduced by sodium sulphide or tin (only a slight excess of tin used) and hydrochloric acid. It was a pale pellow, microcrystalline powder, crystallising from hot water, m.p. 150° after softening at about 120°. (Found : N, 15'9. $C_{12}H_{13}O_2N_3S$ requires N, 16'0 per cent).

N-(*p*-Nitrobenzylsulphonyl)-sulphanilamide.—Sulphanilamide (1.72 g.) and *p*-nitrobenzylsulphonyl chloride (2.4 g.) were ground together and the orange-red product was heated in pyridine for a few minutes. It was then neutralised by adding dilute acid and the separated solid was purified by thrice crystallisation from acetic acid, m.p. 199-200°. (Found: N, 11.3. $C_{13}H_{13}O_6N_3S_2$ requires N, 11.32 per cent). It is very soluble in acetone and pyridine, moderately in alcohol and acetic acid, and sparingly in hot water.

N-(*p*-Aminobenzylsulphonyl)-sulphanilamide was obtained by the reduction of the above nitro compound by means of tin and hydrochloric acid similar to the method already described. The hydrochloride crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 175-80° (decomp.) and the free base was obtained by decomposing it with dilute ammonia and crystallising it from hot water. It melts at 162-65° after softening. (Found: N, 12.0. $C_{13}H_{13}O_4N_3S_2$ requires N, 12.32 per cent).

Di-p-Nitrobenzylsulphonamide was obtained by heating two molecules of *p*-nitrobenzylsulphonyl chloride with just the quantity of ammonia or by grinding together with the required amount of ammonium carbonate. It was crystallised from dilute alcohol in big prismatic plates, m.p. 268° (decomp.) readily soluble in water. (Found: N, 9.9. $C_{14}H_{13}O_6N_3S_2$ requires N, 10.12 per cent).

Di-p-aminobenzylsulphonamide was prepared by reducing the above nitro compound by means of sodium sulphide (2 mols.) in the usual manner, or by tin and hydrochloric acid when a crystalline hydrochloride of the substance was obtained (the reaction was carried out in a similar manner to that described for the preparation of *p*-aminobenzylsulphanilide). It decomposed without melting at about 275° and yielded the free amino compound when just neutralised with ammonia. The free diamino compound crystallised from hot water in almost colourless needles and decomposed without melting. (Found: N, 11.6. $C_{14}H_{17}O_4N_3S_2$ requires N, 11.83 per cent).

I wish to express my sincere gratitude to Prof. P. C. Guha, D.Sc., F.N.I., for his kind interest in this work, and to the Lady Tata Memorial Trust for the award of a scholarship which has enabled me to take up this investigation.